

Supporting researchers in Archaeology with Diamond Open Access. The experience of *Transformations. A DARIAH Journal*

Françoise Gouzi, Anne Baillot, Toma Tasovac (DARIAH-EU)

CAA Athens 2025 - Session 30 (May 6th)

CC-BY 4.0

TRANSFORMATIONS
A DARIAH Journal

How aware is the archaeological community of OS practices

- Researchers face access issues (cultural heritage) or legal constraints;
- Heterogeneity of data collection and documentation processes;
- Lack of contextual knowledge about how research data (paradata) was created and curated (Huvila, 2022);
- Much of the past and ongoing focus has been directed to the documentation of archaeological 3D data;
- Recent changes in research policy and research funding recognise data sharing as a necessary condition for scientific innovation.

Key challenges in data sharing and reusability

- Our publishing model is based on DIAMOND OA;
- Overlay Journals combine elements from the gold and green routes to (OA), which have often been presented as separate paths to enable OA;
- The data and metadata produced are open, standardised, structured, easily accessible and interoperable;
- The FAIR guiding principles have been instrumental in establishing a clear path for data stewardship, significantly advancing the management, dissemination, and utilization of scientific data (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Linking publications to data, workflows and tools

Special attention to Data availability and reuse in the evaluation process

- Data accessible in trusted repository
- Data collection reproducible
- Structured and accurate metadata (formats, PIDs, data integrity,...)
- Data re-usable (licenses, interoperability)

Supporting the heterogeneity of data formats & standards

The ATRIUM peer review framework aims to incentivise a wide variety of research outputs that are necessary for building and maintaining innovative research infrastructures

A workflow paper is defined as a scientific publication that outlines the work steps in a defined research process. It sheds light on the context in which the workflow was developed and applied in the first place, and demonstrates which usages can be envisioned. It also addresses the challenges to its reusability.

Training materials are a type of research output explicitly created to help individuals learn or develop specific skills, knowledge or competencies.

A data paper describes a particular dataset, or a group of datasets, including the circumstances of their collection and their potential utility and gives access to the dataset.

Incentivising researchers to share a diversity of research outputs

1. Supporting diversity and processes as a Research Infrastructure

We are advocating for process-based evaluation systems that recognize and reward all types of significant findings that may have been produced during the research process and not only in the final journal publication or a monograph.

2. Supporting innovation as a RI

Enduring role of the Arts and Humanities in driving societal change

3. Incentivise Open Peer Review (OPR)

OPR enhances the **quality, reliability and effectiveness** of the Peer Review process

4. Best practices and editorial quality standards

- International standards for Open Access Journals;
- [DOAJ seal](#): long-term preservation, use of PID, discoverability, author rights;
- Improve Open Access policy (copyright and licensing, business model and editorial management) and metadata quality

To conclude!

[UNESCO](#) recommendation for OS (2021) calls for "supporting not-for-profit, academic and scientific community-driven publishing models as a common good";

DARIAH maintains and operates an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices and sustains researchers in using them to build, analyse and interpret digital resources.

How to contribute as author or reviewer

Second call for contributions coming soon!

<https://transformations.episciences.org>

Editorial Board of *Transformations - DARIAH Journal*

Toma Tasovac, Editor-in-Chief

Anne Baillot and Françoise Gouzi, Managing Editors

Eliza Papaki, Communication Officer

Contact: transformations@episciences.org

CoARA WG. (2024). Recognizing and rewarding peer review activities of scholarly articles, books, and funding proposals - Draft recommendations from the CoARA Working Group on Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review.

<https://coara.eu/working-groups/working-groups/wg-recognizing-and-rewarding-peer-review/>

Gouzi, F., Mrugalski, M., & Odebrecht, C. (2024). D5.3 Toolkit for report for data sharing between researchers and institutions in the field of literary studies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742612> also available in this Wiki: https://clsinfra.io/toolkit_data_sharing/

Gouzi, F. (2024). DARIAH overlay journal as an alternative and transparent publishing model *in* OPERAS Innovation Lab blog <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/02/20/dariah-overlay-journal-as-an-alternative-and-transparent-publishing-model/> [accessed 25.04.25]

Huvila, Isto. "Improving the usefulness of research data with better paradata" *Open Information Science*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2022, pp. 28-48. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opis-2022-0129>

Maryl, M., Wnuk, M., Gouzi, F., & Umerle, T. (2024). Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221728>

Toma Tasovac, Laurent Romary, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Rahel C. Ackermann, Daniel Alves, et al. (2023). The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper. hal-04136772

Viola, Lorella. 2023. *The Humanities in the Digital: Beyond Critical Digital Humanities*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.